

Towards Wireless 5G Operating Room

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Purpose

Augmented Reality (AR) applications have strong growth potential in clinical practices such as needle biopsy and surgery guidance and require important amounts of video data to be transferred with very low latency. In this context, devices and wires see their numbers grow in the Operating Room (OR) and a way to reduce this number is to use 5G transmission. The goal of this paper is to start demonstrating and measuring 5G capabilities inside the OR by setting up a real time AR application merging images from two medical modalities and over a 5G network. To provide a precise synchronization of the different incoming images, we will operate DICOM-RTV [1] (Real Time video) streams.

Methods

Fig. 1 Setup simulating a wireless operating room in b<>com show room at Rennes

The scenario considers a situation where a patient has to undergo a cardiac intervention procedure based on live, simultaneous fluoroscopy and ultrasound (US) imaging. To create the AR application merging US and X-ray images, two calibrations should be performed beforehand in order to get the spatial relationship between the two planes. [2] presents the US probe calibration method. Concerning X-ray calibration, aimed at evaluating the X-ray device projective parameters, we performed a geometrical 2D/3D calibration using a dedicated 3D-printed cubic phantom with embedded radiopaque fiducials (small metal balls). This calibration was tested on a Siemens AXIOM Artis C-Arm in TherA-Image Platform at University Hospital Rennes.

Fig.1 represents the setup to simulate a wireless OR, as a first step, in b<>com Rennes showroom. As illustrated on the figure, we used a BCOM Platform containing 4 servers in a transportable suitcase. C-arms are generally heavily connected, so we did not set up a 5G transmission and directly connected an X-ray simulator video output to the first server (DICOM-RTV Tx) to be transformed into a DICOM-RTV stream. We then connected the ArtUS Telemed US to a laptop to grab ultrasound images. The

laptop also contains a software to track US probe using the same framework as for US calibration (see RGB-D based tracking described in [2]). The probe's pose matrix is then sent in the metadata flow associated with US video flow. The laptop supplies these flows to a DICOM-RTV Transmitter (a 2nd Tx for US) equipped with a video compression board. The Tx delivers a 1080p@59.94Hz video signal, and video is compressed using an HEVC ULL (High Efficiency Video Coding Ultra Low Latency) codec. The compressed flow is sent to an ASKEY CPE (Customer Premises Equipment) which communicates with the 5G antenna as an uplink transmission. Once both DICOM-RTV Tx are activated, the AR application in the second server (AR Apps) exploits incoming flows to create a spatial fusion of US and X-ray images. The US video is projected onto the background X-ray image in a spatially coherent manner, and overlaid using transparency.

The result of this process (a 720p@20Hz uncompressed signal) is sent to a DICOM-RTV Rx, responsible for displaying the AR view on a monitor, using 5G downlink transmission. A third server (PTP Oregano), hosting an Oregano syn1588® board, allows to synchronize all devices using PTP (Precision Time Protocol). The last server (UPF) contains the User Plane Function to communicate with NOKIA's Radio Access Network (RAN) and transmit data between CPE and applications servers. We based our Control Plane on b<>com WEF (Wireless Edge Factory) solution deployed in b<>com data center to manage network signalization. Finally, the 5G antenna was placed and oriented at 4.5 meters to the CPE to respect OR typical dimensions. We based our network on 5G NSA (Non Standalone) architecture and used the 26GHz frequency band, 5G NR n257 frequency band and 100MHz channel bandwidth, with a backup 4G network of 2.6GHz B38 band and 20MHz channel bandwidth.

Results

To validate qualitatively our AR application, the cubic calibration phantom was filled with water. Visually coherent results were observed by checking on the AR application that cube's edges in US images fit edges in X-ray image correctly. Further tests are planned to quantify the X-ray calibration precision based on reprojection error, and to quantify global calibration error using a dedicated validation phantom. To evaluate uplink bandwidth limitations, we tuned the Tx video compression rate and were able to send at 100Mbps without loss. On the downlink transmission, we tested several video framerates and observed no packet loss at 20 fps (480Mbps). At 25 fps (580Mbps) some packets started to be missing and at 30 fps (700 Mbps) the image quality was degraded. End to end latency is around 300ms which is currently not acceptable for clinical practice. This latency is mainly due to application processing and to the final restitution framerate (20Hz). 5G latency is estimated around 15ms and is so not impacting significantly image restitution.

Conclusion

5G in the OR can make equipment easier to install, to connect and can help sterilization. This setup allowed to test a complete real time AR solution over 5G and helped assessing 5G possibilities and limitations. 100Mbps were transferred uplink and 480Mbps downlink without loss. Future work should include a validation of X-ray calibration accuracy and a global calibration error quantification. AR application performance needs to be improved before a final demonstration in University Hospital Rennes to gather clinicians' feedbacks. However, this constitutes a promising step towards a 5G connected OR.

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References

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